

EELISA

European University

**COMMON EELISA MECHANISM TO ENABLE, INCENTIVIZE,
MEASURE AND AWARD OS PRACTICES**

Deliverable 3.5

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Common EELISA mechanism to enable, incentivize, measure and award OS practices

- for the use of EELISA InnoCORE partners-
Version 1.0

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Introduction

This report is Deliverable D3.5 of the EELISA INNOvation and COmmon REsearch Strategy Project (EELISA INNOCORE). It focuses on a **Common EELISA Mechanism to Enable, Incentivize, Measure, and Award Open Science Practices**. The report includes policies, practices, and developments that could guide research-performing organizations (RPOs), such as universities, in their efforts to promote and recognize Open Science (OS). The deliverable concentrates on the Incentives and Rewards dimension of OS (OS I&R). It proposes a digital mechanism designed to enhance the exchange of practices and promote mutual learning across the consortium.

D3.5 is based on key developments, including the [OS Toolkit](#), the [OS Strategic Planning and Implementation Guide](#), and the OS Strategic Plans (OSAPs). Additionally, it builds on key policy developments and frameworks, practical tools and interventions (refer to Annex 1 for a comprehensive selection):

- [San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment](#) (DORA);
- UNESCO Open Access policy development guidelines (Swan, 2012);
- [Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics](#) (Hicks et al., 2015);
- [OS-CAM Matrix](#) (European Commission, 2017);
- Recommendations by the Open Science Policy Platform (European Commission, 2018);
- Hong Kong Principles (Moher et al., 2019);
- the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#) (CoARA);
- [Perspectives on the new European Research Area from the university sector](#)"
- Universities without walls: A vision for 2030 (EUA, 2021);
- [Next Generation Metrics](#) (Bauer et al., 2020);
- UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (UNESCO, 2021);
- [Marseille Declaration on International Cooperation in Research and Innovation](#)
- [Lund Declaration on Research Infrastructures](#)
- European [Charter for Researchers](#);
- European Competence Framework for Researchers ([ResearchComp](#)).

Furthermore, D3.5 emphasizes **key messages** from the analysis of the policies and initiatives referenced in Annex 1.

- **Redefining Open Science: Beyond Research to Career Pathways and Recognition Systems.** A primary insight from the landscaping analysis is that Open Science's significance extends beyond just research; it should also be pivotal in shaping new academic career trajectories and recognition frameworks. Additionally, the reform of research assessment paves the way for fresh perspectives and deeper insights. A distinction exists between 'research' and 'researcher' assessment systems. While the former concentrates solely on research-centric endeavors, the latter is expansive, encompassing all activities undertaken by researchers, both research-related and otherwise. It is vital to recognize the variability in research paradigms, educational systems, and regulations across Europe, warranting adaptive and flexible systems as opposed to a singular universal approach.
- **Scope of Current Assessments:** Existing researcher assessment mechanisms are overly reliant on peer-reviewed outputs and their citations in premier journals. A holistic revision is advocated, proposing a bifurcated approach, dividing into research and non-research dimensions. The former should trace the entirety of the research journey, from inception to dissemination. In contrast, the latter should be comprehensive, covering activities like teaching, mentorship, project management, and scientific communication.

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- **Open Science Integration:** Assessment methodologies should align with the prevailing OS-oriented policies at national, European, and global levels. A revised researcher assessment approach should have open and non-open facets. The 'open' facet should chronicle outputs that are made public, including open-access publications, FAIR data, open peer reviews, and open educational resources. Conversely, the 'non-open' dimension should register outputs that remain restricted or confidential.
- **Quantitative vs. Qualitative Assessments:** A significant theme in the literature is the excessive focus on quantitative bibliometrics. The call is for a broader perspective, incorporating a range of alternative metrics, or 'altmetrics'. The proposed assessment framework should juxtapose quantitative and qualitative measures. Such a system would empower universities and funders with diverse options for recruitment, career advancement, grant allocation, and OS promotion. However, while utilizing metrics, vigilance against potential misuse and manipulation is essential, ensuring malpractices are promptly addressed during execution.
- **Design evaluations with the evaluated.** Both research performing and research funding organizations should collaboratively design and analyze research evaluations, involving both active researchers and their supporters (Curry, de Rijcke, et al., 2022). Next-gen metrics are poised to address these. Following the 2015 "Metric Tide" (Wilsdon et al., 2015), the 2017 report (European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. et al., 2017) emphasized open science's integration into society and offered 12 recommendations in line with European goals. CESAER's 2020 white paper (Bauer et al., 2020) advocates for quality and trust over competition in research assessment. UKRI's ongoing FRAP initiative aims to pinpoint a robust research system's characteristics, reducing academic bureaucracy. Lastly, the Hong Kong Principles (Moher et al., 2019) champion those enhancing research trustworthiness.

Aiming to establish a unified mechanism for promoting OS practices, incentives, recognition, and rewards, the document delves into **Section 2** which provides definitions of both rewards and incentives, as well as strategies and practices that support OS incentives and rewards. Following this, **Section 3** introduces principles and showcases examples of indicators suitable for assessing researchers at RFOs. **Section 4** highlights recent shifts in research assessment, details the contributions made by CoARA, and unveils the architecture of the digital common mechanism for EELISA INNOCORE - the **EELISA COsMPAS (Common Open Science Mechanism for Practices, Assessment, and Support)**.

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Section 2. Definitions, strategies, and actions for enhancing Open Science incentives and rewards

2.1 Rewards and Incentives: Their Role and Impact

Both rewards and incentives are pivotal instruments that can profoundly influence individuals' or teams' motivation, actions, and overall performance. Their primary function is to promote specific behaviours, boost efficiency, and cultivate a positive working atmosphere.

Rewards are often provided post an achieved action or behaviour. Their primary objective is to bolster or advocate for such behaviour. They serve as a reflection on the agent's performance, directing it towards its goals. These acknowledgements can be material, or non-material, like commendations or acknowledgment.

Incentives, on the other hand, are primarily motivational tools, offered to prompt certain actions or behaviours. These motivational triggers can range from monetary benefits, acclaim, advancements, to other positive affirmations. Typically, incentives are presented in anticipation of an action, aiming to spur individuals into taking it.

While the terms 'rewards' and 'incentives' are frequently used synonymously, they possess distinct nuances, especially concerning their intent, timing, and effect on worker motivation and actions. Table 1 presents the primary differences between rewards and incentives:

Table 1. Differences between rewards and incentives

Basis	Rewards	Incentives
Purpose	Rewards serve as recognition and appreciation for past performance, accomplishments, or contributions of employees. They help strengthen the relationship between the organization and the employee by acknowledging their hard work.	Incentives are meant to motivate and influence future behaviour or performance by offering a specific benefit or compensation for achieving predetermined goals.
Timing	Rewards are retrospective and given after an employee has achieved a goal or completed a task. They act as a form of acknowledgement for the employee's hard work.	Incentives are prospective and announced beforehand, providing employees with a clear objective to work towards to receive the promised benefit.
Impact on motivation	Rewards can boost employee morale and satisfaction by acknowledging their accomplishments and making them feel valued.	Incentives, however, create a sense of anticipation and motivation for future performance by offering employees an additional reason to strive for better results.
Tangibility	Rewards can be both tangible such as monetary rewards, gifts, and promotions, and intangible such as recognition, praise, or appreciation.	Incentives are often more tangible, as they usually involve a clearly defined benefit or compensation that employees can expect upon achieving a specific goal.
Flexibility	Rewards can be more flexible, as they may be given on an ad-hoc basis or	Incentives are usually tied to specific targets or milestones, making them less

Basis	Rewards	Incentives
	as part of a regular performance review process.	flexible in terms of when they can be awarded.
Conditionality	Rewards are typically unconditional, as they are given in recognition of past achievements without any further requirements.	Incentives, however, are conditional, as they are only provided if an employee meets or surpasses the specified goals or objectives.
Distribution	Rewards can be distributed more broadly within an organization, as they can be given to employees for various achievements or performance levels.	Incentives are often tied to specific targets, making their distribution more limited to those who meet the established criteria.
Performance measures	Rewards can be based on a range of performance measures, including individual or team achievements, subjective evaluations, etc.	Incentives are generally based on clearly defined, measurable goals or objectives provided by the organisation.

2.2 Encouraging or incentivising open science practices

Effective promotion of OS requires a comprehensive strategy that integrates various activities and incentives. Institutions are encouraged to craft strategies that incorporate such activities and incentives. Given the vast diversity in education and research across disciplines, it is improbable that a singular initiative or incentive will uniformly promote OS. A comprehensive approach that amalgamates various activities and progressively builds upon them annually can drive change. Universities may want to think about formulating a strategy that integrates some of the following incentives listed below (see Figure 1). The examples are drawn from international contexts.

Figure 1. Strategies to encourage open science

Adapted from <https://caul.libguides.com/open-research-toolkit/incentives>

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Demonstrate Institutional Commitment to OS

Showcasing the institution's dedication to open research and more broadly to open science is crucial for fostering its adoption within the organization and aiding researchers in embracing OS practices. Some strategic approaches encompass:

Box 1. Strategic approaches to OS

- Pledge allegiance to the principles of the [Declaration on Research Assessment \(DORA\)](#), the [Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics](#) and the [Hong Kong Principles for Assessing Researchers](#), and the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#);
- Incorporate a Key Performance Indicator (KPI) emphasizing open access, open research, open educational resources or citizen science activities within the institution's strategic blueprints, departmental action plans, or yearly summaries.
- Foster a transparent academic environment by initiatives like making internal research discussions available to the general public, curating public lecture series, participating actively in Open Access Week, and organizing domain-specific community outreach and engagement sessions.
- Advocate for and bolster citizen-led scientific endeavors and collaboratively shape research endeavors with participant input.
- Designate scholarly leaders within distinct fields to champion and drive the open research paradigm in their respective disciplines.
- Apply for the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R) seal, and actively support the European Charter for Researchers.

Provide Infrastructure

Institutions can bolster open research initiatives by developing a robust infrastructure that streamlines and enhances the experience for researchers delving into open research methods. To achieve this:

Box 2. Approaches to proving infrastructure

- Develop a dedicated open research platform, tailored to cater to specific disciplinary needs.
- Implement systems that facilitate researchers in acquiring a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for their work, ensuring traceability and easy referencing.

Provide support for OS

Box 3. Approaches to supporting OS

- Facilitate streamlined publication processes, ensuring that both the author's accepted manuscript version and pre-prints are seamlessly integrated into the institution's repository.

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- Offer specialized guidance and allocate resources in data science to help researchers align their data with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles, promoting openness.
- Advocate for exemplary research data management by assisting in the formulation of comprehensive data management plans.
- Aid researchers in procuring Digital Object Identifiers for their datasets, bolstering traceability and credibility.
- Commit institutional resources for expansive participation at both the national and international levels, such as subsidizing participation in open research symposiums, endorsing involvement in domain-specific committees, and patronizing open research activities.
- Direct specialized institutional backing towards researchers actively involved in open methodologies.
- Tailor support strategies that align with the institution's recognized areas of distinction.
- Champion joint ventures that focus on domain-specific endeavors and innovations.

Promote OS

Box 4. Approaches to promoting OS

- Profile OS ambassadors.
- Spotlight and celebrate the contributions of OS champions.
- Highlight and commend researchers actively participating in open research practices in major internal communications.
- Promote open access publications, especially those with cross-disciplinary appeal, through platforms like social media to reach audiences beyond the academic sphere.
- Curate and present a relevant array of events and sessions during Open Access Week.
- Organize instructive and interactive sessions tailored for budding researchers to deepen their engagement with open research practices.

Incentivize OS

Box 5. Approaches to incentivising OS

- Mandate that all internally-funded research projects commit to publishing their outputs via open access channels.
- Allocate dedicated funds to assist researchers in publishing in premier, wholly open access journals.
- Launch mini-grant initiatives that champion open research methodologies, such as facilitating researchers in disclosing data or attending conferences focused on open research.
- Incorporate a clear track record of commitment to open access or open research as a key criterion for staff advancements and new appointments.
- Roll out a recognition scheme that celebrates and honors exemplary open research endeavors.

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2.3 Recognition and Rewarding of OS

The acknowledgment and reward system for OS practices extend beyond the confines of standard evaluation and assessment measures. To truly champion the adoption of OS, it's essential that these practices are integrated within the broader **frameworks of academic career progression**, utilizing metrics judiciously and ensuring their responsible application.

A comprehensive career development policy should follow these stages:

Integration of OS in Formal Evaluation

Recognize and incorporate OS practices within standard evaluation and assessment procedures.

OS Assessment in Research

Establish an evaluation process that considers Open Science practices when assessing rewards, promotions, or tenure opportunities.

Embedding in Career Policies:

The assessment should be firmly grounded within a wider career strategy. This strategy should responsibly incorporate relevant metrics and be aligned with the latest directives on career evaluation and education.

To embed open science as a staple practice rather than a transient trend, it is imperative to harmonize incentives that benefit both the scientific community and society at large, with those that drive individual academic progression.

It is important to highlight that **rewards** manifest in diverse manners. Open Science practices can be a metric in evaluating various stages of a researcher's career. While a **reward** in the conventional sense recognizes past achievements, it's crucial to also consider anticipatory **incentives** that guide forthcoming actions. Although the tools or metrics for evaluation might vary depending on the context, the overarching principles supporting Open Science remain consistent.

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Figure 2. Examples of OS Rewards

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2.4. International perspectives on OS incentives and rewards

KU Leuven's Commitment to OS Recognition and Reward

[KU Leuven](#) is deeply committed to fostering an environment where academics can cultivate flexible and enduring careers, maximizing their unique talents. Additionally, the institution recognizes the importance of balancing professional pursuits with other vital life aspects. In line with this commitment, KU Leuven has formulated clear policies and transparently shared them with the public to underscore their dedication to these principles.

Open Science Community Utrecht

[Open Science Community Utrecht](#) (OSCU) was initiated to expedite the adoption of Open Science practices, particularly targeting those new to the field. Its objectives include: (1) fostering the exchange of Open Science practices among colleagues, (2) motivating and assisting researchers to take their initial or subsequent modest steps into the realm of Open Science, (3) contributing to Open Science policies, infrastructures, and support services, thereby moulding the transition to Open Science, and (4) investigating and encouraging collaborations between academics and societal stakeholders for mutual inspiration and co-creation.

École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne: Open Science Fund

The [EPFL Open Science Fund](#) provides financial support to EPFL researchers. This fund is dedicated to projects that promote and implement open research practices across various platforms, encompassing scholarly articles, data sets, software, hardware, and methodologies.

The Imperial Open Access Fund

The Imperial Open Access Fund ([Imperial Fund](#)) at Imperial College London offers financial assistance to authors for open access publishing, especially targeting those who haven't secured research grant funding or those without external financial support for their work.

Open Research Award

The University of Groningen Library in collaboration with the Open Science Community Groningen (OSCG) have initiated the [Open Research Award](#), a celebration of transparency and accessibility in research and teaching.

This award recognizes the diverse efforts of academics in making their research or teaching processes more transparent, accessible, or reproducible. Both researchers and students have the opportunity to present case studies that detail their direct experiences with open research and educational methodologies, either as individuals or as groups. These submissions should ideally delve into the advantages, challenges, and intricacies of adopting open strategies, and share both successes and lessons learned. The aim is to capture genuine narratives that shed light on the motivations behind choosing (or

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refraining from) open approaches, providing a well-considered analysis of the benefits and potential pitfalls of such decisions

The Dutch initiative 'Room for Everyone's Talent'

In 2019, the Dutch position paper "[Room for Everyone's Talent](#)" encapsulated pressing academic debates. Stemming from initiatives like the Netherlands' Open Science Agenda and critiques of metric-based evaluations, it highlighted broader academic culture issues and the need for diversified recognition. Influenced by Ruth Graham's [Teaching Framework](#) and backed by major Dutch academic entities, it marked a call for holistic academic reform. It advocates for a diversified recognition of academic contributions. Shifting focus from publication quantity to encompass wider academic roles, it addresses the evolving expectations of academic institutions and societal needs. The paper emphasizes five key objectives: varied **career pathways**, balanced **individual and group evaluations**, prioritizing **quality and creativity** in assessments, promotion of **Open Science** with accessible research outcomes, and fostering **academic leadership** at all levels.

NOR-CAM - A toolbox for recognition and rewards

A task force set up by Universities Norway (UHR) was given the responsibility of suggesting guiding principles for the evaluation of research and researchers, particularly in the context of the shift to Open Science. The group advocates for a more adaptable and all-encompassing approach to acknowledging accomplishments in academic research. The objective has been to craft a guideline rooted in three foundational principles of evaluation: enhanced transparency, inclusivity of various research dimensions, and thorough evaluations instead of a narrow focus on indicators. The joint work resulted in the NOR-CAM ([The Norwegian Career Assessment Matrix](#)) as a structured system that evaluates and integrates these components for diverse objectives. This enriched approach to research evaluation seeks to motivate and applaud a wider array of academic endeavors, ultimately enriching academic culture and elevating research quality.

Open Science Rewards and Incentives Registry

The [Registry](#)'s objective is to establish a collaborative space where various stakeholders can share not only their plans but also the results of pilots and other endeavors specifically targeting the academic reward system. We are now accepting submissions showcasing such initiatives..

Publisher Agreements at University of Exeter

The university offers funding opportunities for researchers aiming to publish in completely open access journals. Additionally, due to the university's [transformative agreements](#) with publishers, authors have the advantage of publishing open access either without incurring any article processing charges or at a significantly reduced rate.

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Recognition and Rewards Vision at University of Utrecht

Their [vision](#) outlines a set of guiding principles that shape procedures related to employee recruitment, selection, integration, training, development, performance evaluation, and advancement.

The Academic Promotions Frameworks at University of Bristol and University of Glasgow

The university's updated [criteria](#) for academic promotion now encompass open research practices. Similarly, at the University of Glasgow, individuals seeking promotion are anticipated to showcase outputs that align with both funder guidelines and the Research Excellence Framework standards for [open access](#). They should also embody the highest standards of open research practices.

Key insights

The synthesis of incentives and rewards outlined in Box 6 presents a comprehensive approach that could be effectively embraced by the consortium. The compilation provides pathways, illustrating varied mechanisms for fostering and enhancing open science practices.

Box 6. Key insights for EELISA InnoCORE on the use of incentives and rewards

- Rewards for open science contributions can take various forms, and they often serve as incentives to encourage researchers to engage in more transparent and collaborative practices. It's important to note that rewards for open science should align with the goals and values of the research community and institutions. The specific rewards offered may vary widely depending on the field of research, the level of openness desired, and the policies and resources available within an institution or organization. Here are some examples of rewards for open science:
 - **Funding Opportunities:**
 - Grants and funding opportunities specifically designed for open science projects (e.g., an **EELISA InnoCORE Connect OS call for projects**).
 - Access to research funding or resources based on successful open science initiatives.
 - **Awards and Prizes:**
 - Open science awards and prizes that recognize outstanding contributions, such as:
 - Open data awards.
 - Open source software awards.
 - Collaborative research awards.
 - **Collaboration Opportunities:**
 - Access to collaborative networks and opportunities facilitated by institutions or organizations that promote open science.
 - **Recognition Events:**
 - Participation in recognition events, such as open science symposiums, workshops, or conferences, where EELISA researchers can showcase their work and receive acknowledgment. Moreover, librarians play a pivotal role in open science and should be engaged in these events.
 - **Public Engagement:**
 - Enhance public recognition for open science contributions by highlighting the societal benefits of transparent research. Consider

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showcasing good practice examples in the EELISA OS community, curating an **OS Newsletter**, or introducing an **Open Science section** in the existing **EELISA newsletter**.

- Professional Development
 - Support for professional development, including training, workshops, or courses related to open science practices.
- Institutional Support:
 - Institutional support in the form of infrastructure for data storage, sharing, and management, along with funding for open science projects.
 - Opportunities to join and contribute to a supportive open science community that values and rewards openness and collaboration

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Section 3. Towards an EELISA INNOCORE common mechanism for OS recognition and rewards

3.1 Practices identified among EELISA partners

The document D3.5 establishes the foundation for a unified EELISA mechanism, termed the EELISA COsMPAS, which focuses on OS recognition and rewards. Central to this mechanism is the exchange of experiences and best practices among partners. The information in this section is based on findings from the institutional survey carried out for D3.1. As such, the described practices may have since been enhanced or supplemented by new initiatives and, therefore, they are not exhaustive.

The practices were organized in four categories, following the proposal in Figure 1.: **institutional commitment** (Box 7), **providing support** (Box 8), **promoting OS** (Box 9), and **incentives for OS** (Box 10).

Box 7. EELISA INNOCORE OS I&R practices for category institutional commitment

- UPM: Signatory/member of EOSC, the Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI), Berlin Declaration on Open Access, and more, demonstrating a strong commitment to open science.
- FAU: Actively advocates for open science, with both faculty and researchers encouraged to publish openly. It was the first university in Germany to adopt an Open Science Policy on October 13, 2021
- SSSA: Emphasizes the promotion of open access through its activities and has integrated open science into its mission.

Box 8. EELISA INNOCORE OS I&R practices for category Providing Support

UPM:

- The library manages the digital archive for open access publications.
- The 'Open Science' community was established to foster open science practices.
- The International Projects Office supports participation in international projects and organizes training activities related to Open Science.

FAU: Supplies platforms and repositories for open access, and assists researchers in understanding open access requirements.

- The university supports open access publication with a central open access publication fund.
- FAU's guidelines for handling digital research data, known as 'Research data policy'

SSSA: Encourages open science practices through its internal policies and has organized training programs.

UPB has developed an e-Learning course on OS and an institutional repository has been developed. The PubArt program is a dedicated fund for OA publishing

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Box 9. EELISA INNOCORE OS I&R practices for category Promoting Open Science

UPM: Open access to scientific publications is deeply rooted with the existence of POLI-RED for journals and the digital archive for publications. Research data management is also prioritized with platforms like E-Ciencia Datos.

FAU: Pushes for mandates requiring open access for publications from publicly funded research. Offers platforms to ensure open availability of research data. They are encouraging the use of open educational resources for collaboration and innovation in teaching.

SSSA: Actively promotes open access through various platforms, ensuring that both research outputs and data are available and adhere to FAIR principles.

Box 10. EELISA INNOCORE OS I&R practices for category Incentivizing Open Science

UPM: Uses the Plan for Quality Assessment of Research and Innovation, which focuses on evaluating research structures instead of individual researchers. This is applied to internal UPM calls. The assessment does not distinctly reward open access publications.

FAU: Implements reward mechanisms that explicitly support open science. Bibliometric data are also used in research evaluation.

SSSA: While detailed assessment methods weren't provided, the institution's push for open science likely influences its research assessment policies and incentives.

3.2 Next generation metrics for responsible research assessment

Next-generation metrics emerge as advanced tools, paving the way for a comprehensive evaluation of scholarly research and academic activities. Moving beyond traditional measures like citation counts and impact factors, these metrics offer an in-depth insight into the research impact and outreach. A combination of quantitative and qualitative measures, alongside expert opinions, is essential for understanding the openness in scientific research. The goal remains to focus on evaluating significant and impactful aspects within a framework marked by openness and transparency.

However, infusing Open Science practices into responsible research assessment is not a straightforward task. Traditional assessment methods from current bibliometrics cannot be directly applied within the evolving Open Science ecosystem. The one-size-fits-all approach falls short in assessing research in this emerging field. This transition necessitates a more adaptable and diverse assessment framework in tune with Open Science principles.

In response to this, the [GraspOS Project](#) introduces a collaboratively developed Open Science Assessment Framework (OSAF). This framework is intended to document and offer insights on aligning indicators and tools with the specific characteristics of the assessment context, such as the disciplinary and institutional context and assessment levels – see Figure 3.

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Figure 3 The GraspOS Open Science Assessment Framework

Source: [The GraspOS Project](#)

Discussion on metrics and indicators underscores the differences, challenges, and opportunities arising from **qualitative** and **quantitative approaches**. These encompass scientific excellence, peer review, and quality cultures. A clear distinction is established among indicators related to **input**, **process**, **output**, and **impact**. A blend of these indicators often yields the most beneficial insights.

Traditional metrics like bibliometric indicators have seen extensive use for evaluating scientific performance and other aspects. With the ongoing reform in research assessment, a reevaluation and adjustment of these indicators are imperative. The objective is to align them with the principles of responsible research assessment, ensuring the evaluation not only rewards but also mirrors the diverse qualities of exceptional research, thus promoting a diverse and inclusive research environment.

In revising the indicators, certain dimensions outlined in Box 11 are to be considered, ensuring a robust and comprehensive approach to research assessment in the realm of Open Science (Curry, de Rijcke, et al., 2022).

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Box 11. A revised framework for responsible metrics

A revised framework for responsible metrics (Curry, Gadd, et al., 2022, p. 24)

Responsible metrics are founded on the principle that the qualities of research reside both in the outputs and impacts of research work, and in the way it is conducted. They have the following dimensions:

- **Robustness:** basing metrics on the best possible data in terms of accuracy and scope;
- **Humility:** recognising that quantitative indicators should not supplant qualitative, expert assessment, but should be used where appropriate to strengthen or complement peer review;
- **Transparency:** opening up data collection and analytical processes, so those being evaluated are included in the design of the evaluations and can test and verify the results;
- **Diversity:** accounting for variation by field, and using a range of indicators to reflect and support a plurality of research, of research and research-enabling 84 staff characteristics, and researcher career paths across the system;
- **Reflexivity:** recognising and anticipating the systemic and potential effects of indicators, and updating them in response.

More recently, the Open and Universal Science Project (OPUS) has proposed a Researcher Assessment Framework ([RAF](#)) presenting 'realistic indicators and metrics to monitor and drive Open Science'. The RAF is built on 10 guiding principles (see Box 12):

Box 12. 10 guiding principles supporting the OPUS RAF

1. Provide a comprehensive framework of indicators and metrics for RPOs and RFOs
2. Provide a framework which applies across countries, disciplines, and organisations
3. Provide a framework which combines both quantitative and qualitative assessment
4. Focus on the assessment of individual researchers and not teams, groups, or units
5. Cover the full spectrum of activities by researchers and not just research activities
6. Offer a generic framework which allows open and non-open activities by researchers
7. Offer a specific framework which focuses on Open Science activities by researchers
8. Distinguish process, output, and outcome indicators to capture the lifecycle of activities
9. Formulate indicators and metrics at a high level of description for universal application
10. Leave selection, refinement, and prioritisation of indicators and metrics to RPOs and RFOs

The RAF neither gives precedence to any generic or Open Science indicators and metrics nor does it dictate their selection. Instead, it entrusts the choice and prioritization of these indicators and metrics to RPOs and RFOs. Organizations are empowered to choose and possibly combine indicators and metrics from both generic and Open Science frameworks. They can then refine these chosen metrics, establish priorities, rank and assign weights, and finalize the scoring system for a specific assessment.

The RAF is organized into four primary activity categories. Each of these categories further branches out into subcategories, which subsequently encompass groups of related metrics, as illustrated in Figure 4.

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Figure 4. Categories, Subcategories, and Indicator Groups of RAF

Source: [The OPUS Project](#)

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Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 present a selection of metrics related to OS for the research category. The research category consists of 6 subcategories for proposals, methods, data, software, publications, and materials with Open Science indicators and metrics for researcher assessment. It is to be noted that all the indicators suggested within the OPUS project are of a quantitative nature.

The subcategory of proposals centers on proposals for research projects to a Research Performing Organization (RPO) or Research Funding Organization (RFO), made openly available as indicated in Table 2. The manner in which these proposals are made openly available is flexible.

Table 2. OS Indicators and Metrics for Category Research Subcategory Proposals

Indicator Group	Indicator Type	Quantitative Metric
Proposal Development	Process	# of Developing Project Proposals Openly Available
	Output	# of Submitted Project Proposals Openly Available
	Outcomes	# of Granted Project Proposals Openly Available
		# of Granted Project Proposals involving Open Science

Source: [The OPUS Project](#)

The subcategory of Data emphasizes research data planning, management, and peer review, made openly available as shown in Table 3. It allows flexibility in including or excluding a focus on FAIR principles and in the methods used to make data management plans, data sets, and data peer reviews openly available for public use.

Table 3. OS Indicators and Metrics for Category Research Subcategory Data

Indicator Group	Indicator Type	Quantitative Metrics
Proposal Development	Process	# of (FAIR) Developing Data Management Plans Openly Available
	Output	# of (FAIR) Finalised Data Management Plans Openly Available
	Outcomes	# of (FAIR) Implemented Data Management Plans Openly Available
Data Management	Process	# of Developing (FAIR) Data Sets Openly Available
	Output	# of Finalised (FAIR) Data Sets Openly Available
	Outcomes	# of Archived (FAIR) Data Sets Openly Available
Data Review	Process	# of Draft (FAIR) Data Set Peer Reviews Openly Available
	Output	# of Submitted (FAIR) Data Set Peer Reviews Openly Available

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	Outcomes	# of Accepted (FAIR) Data Set Peer Reviews Openly Available
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Source: [The OPUS Project](#)

Table 4 presents OS indicators and metrics for category research subcategory publications. This subcategory emphasizes research publications and peer reviews, which are made openly available. The approach to making publications and peer reviews openly available is flexible, as is the version of the publication, which could be a preprint, Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM), or Version of Record (VoR). The type of open access—whether green or gold—is also flexible. Additionally, there is flexibility concerning the adherence of the publications to the principles of Plan S.

Table 4. OS Indicators and Metrics for Category Research Subcategory Publications

Indicator Group	Indicator Type	Quantitative Metrics
Publication Drafting	Process	# of Draft Publications Openly Available
	Output	# of Submitted Publications Openly Available
	Outcomes	# of Published Publications Openly Available
		# of Openly Available Publications Accessed
		# of Openly Available Publications Cited
Publication Review	Process	# of Draft Publication Peer Reviews Openly Available
	Output	# of Submitted Publication Peer Reviews Openly Available
	Outcomes	# of Accepted Publication Peer Reviews Openly Available

Source: [The OPUS Project](#)

The indicators and metrics that the RAF provides can be selected and refined according to the interests and needs of RPOs and they could guide the EELISA consortium towards a relevant set of indicators and metrics to be incorporated into the COsMPAS mechanism.

The digital dissemination of research outputs has facilitated the emergence of both traditional metrics like citation data and **alternative metrics** known as **altmetrics**. These include metrics like views, download data, and mentions in various non-scientific publications and platforms. Altmetrics extend beyond the traditional methods of assessing scholarly impact, encompassing social media mentions, downloads, clicks, and other diverse forms of online interaction. This approach allows for real-time insight into the immediate influence and reach of research outputs across a multitude of online platforms (see Table 5. Examples of alternative metrics).

Altmetrics provide a more expansive perspective on the impact and distribution of various research outputs such as articles, datasets, and software. By evaluating data from numerous online platforms, researchers can garner a comprehensive understanding of their work's impact from multiple angles. Beyond the academic realm, altmetrics illuminate the non-academic influence of research, offering valuable insights into public engagement, policy impact, and contributions to society at large.

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Table 5. Examples of alternative metrics

Indicators/metrics	Source/Framework	Definition
Downloads	Metrics toolkit; OpenAIRE UsageCounts; Operas	count of downloads of a journal article or a book or book chapter during a period of time
Download requests, items	Metrics toolkit; OpenAIRE UsageCounts	number of successful item (full-text articles, books and book chapters, software files) download requests
GitHubs: Forks, collaborators, watchers	Metrics toolkit;	“Forks” are created when a user makes a copy of a repository (i.e., a group of files). A “collaborator” is another Github user who is able to perform many actions on the files within the repository, including edits. “Watchers” are Github users who have asked to be notified of activity in a repository, but have not become collaborators.
Altmetric Attention Score	Metrics toolkit	Volume of attention received by a research output across a number of online attention sources

Source: (Hyrkkänen et al., 2023, p. 72)

A recent report of the GraspOS Project (Hyrkkänen et al., 2023) identifies a set of qualitative methods in research assessment that is advisable to complement quantitative metrics (Figure 5).

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Figure 5. Qualitative methods for research assessment

Source: (Hyrkkänen et al., 2023, p. 84)

Qualitative methods are indispensable in research assessment, offering a depth and breadth of insight that complements and enhances quantitative approaches. Their importance is multi-faceted, contributing significantly to a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of research impact.

Firstly, qualitative methods excel in providing a profound understanding of the context within which research operates. They delve into the intricacies and subtleties of the research environment, offering assessors a detailed and rich exploration of the unique contextual factors that quantitative metrics may not fully capture. This depth of insight is vital for a robust and comprehensive research assessment.

Secondly, qualitative methods facilitate the exploration of diverse perspectives within the research landscape. They enable assessors to approach the evaluation from multiple angles, considering the viewpoints of various stakeholders involved, from research participants to community members. This multiplicity of perspectives enhances the richness and depth of the assessment, ensuring that diverse voices and insights are accounted for in the evaluation process.

Furthermore, qualitative methods are instrumental in evaluating the processes that underlie research outcomes. They uncover the 'how' and 'why' behind research results, offering insights into the pathways and mechanisms that lead to impact. This understanding is crucial for assessing not only the outcomes themselves but also the processes that lead to these outcomes, providing a more thorough and holistic evaluation.

In addition, the use of qualitative methods allows for the identification of unanticipated outcomes and impacts. Unlike quantitative metrics, which typically focus on predetermined indicators, qualitative approaches are open-ended, allowing for the emergence of unexpected insights, effects, or impacts. This flexibility is crucial for a comprehensive and authentic assessment of research impact.

Qualitative methods also play a crucial role in identifying and assessing non-quantifiable impacts. They recognize and evaluate outcomes that are not easily measured, such as societal or cultural influence, policy change, and capacity building. This aspect is essential for a holistic assessment that acknowledges the multi-dimensional nature of research impact.

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Moreover, qualitative methods offer constructive and detailed feedback for research enhancement. They provide nuanced insights and recommendations that can inform future research directions, improvements, and innovations, contributing to the continuous enhancement of research quality and impact.

In conclusion, the integration of qualitative methods in research assessment is not just beneficial but essential for a holistic, balanced, and comprehensive evaluation. It ensures that all dimensions of research impact, including those not easily quantifiable, are thoroughly examined, offering a richer, more nuanced understanding and ultimately leading to more robust and informed assessment outcomes.

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Key insights

To ensure the responsible utilization of metrics by the EELISA InnoCORE consortium, list of insights and recommendations is detailed in Box 12.

Box 13. Key insights for EELISA InnoCORE on the use of metrics

- The D3.2 Open Science Strategic Planning and Implementation Guide introduced descriptors and indicators to track and assess advancements in OS implementation. The OS descriptors give a snapshot of the primary features of OS, enabling the partners to articulate their capabilities at a given moment. Meanwhile, the OS indicators supplement these descriptors, serving the function of ongoing observation and evaluation. These suggested indicators drew inspiration from the Open Science Monitor (European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2019). The **indicators will need further adjustments** to be aligned with recent policy developments.
- It is recommended that the consortium develop comprehensive **guidelines** to encourage the responsible use of metrics and indications for the effective planning, monitoring, and evaluation of OS practices. Some of the guiding principles should be:
 - A prevalent practice in research assessments involves integrating both **quantitative and qualitative methodologies**. Nearly all sources emphasize the supplemental role of quantitative metrics, which can be harnessed to furnish empirical evidence for a narrative description.
 - For ensuring process transparency and the correct application of indicators, quantitative indicators ought to be chosen from **metrics that are broadly used and straightforward to comprehend**.
 - Metrics related to Open Science are commonly articulated as the proportion of research outputs available in Open Access. These indicators can be assessed at various levels, including the **research output, individual researcher, and university levels**.
 - While **altmetrics** offer numerous benefits, they also present challenges. It's crucial to approach altmetric data critically, considering the context and source of online engagements. Not all online interactions indicate a positive or meaningful impact, and altmetrics should be used in conjunction with traditional metrics for a well-rounded evaluation.

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Section 4. Where do we go from here?

4.1 Open Science and the reform of research assessment. Principles and commitments

During 2021 the Commission held extensive consultations with European and international stakeholders on the reform of the research assessment summarising the outcomes in a scoping report "[Towards a reform of the research assessment system](#)". At the end of the year, the Commission launched the process towards an agreement on reforming research assessment calling for organisations to express their interest in being part of a coalition for reform. 2022 ended with the publication of the [Agreement for the Reform of Research Assessment](#) and the creation of the [Coalition CoARA](#). The principles for reform are explicitly promoting the recognition and reward of Open Science practices (see Box 14).

Box 14. Reforming Research Assessment. Ten principles

Principles for overarching conditions

- Comply with ethics and integrity rules and practices
- Safeguard freedom of scientific research
- Respect the autonomy of research organisations
- Ensure independence and transparency of the data, infrastructure and criteria

Principles for assessment criteria and processes

- Focus research assessment criteria on quality. Reward the originality of ideas, the professional research conduct, and results beyond the state-of-the-art. Openness of research strongly contributes to quality
- Recognise the contributions that advance knowledge and the (potential) impact of research results (in the short, medium or long-term, and that vary according to disciplines and research types)
- Recognise the diversity of research activities and practices, with a diversity of outputs, and reward early sharing and open collaboration
- Use assessment criteria and processes that respect the variety of scientific disciplines, research types, career stages
- Acknowledge and valorise the diversity in research roles and careers, including roles outside academia
- Ensure gender equality, equal opportunities and inclusiveness.

Four research assessment principles distinctly highlight the significance of open science practices (refer to Box 15):

Box 15. References to open science

- „early sharing of research data and results” is included among the behaviours valued as extended forms of professional and scientific integrity;

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- openness of research (corresponding to “early knowledge and data sharing” and “open collaboration including societal engagement” where appropriate) and “results that are verifiable and reproducible” strongly contribute to quality on which the research assessment should be focused;
- research assessment should recognize the diversity of research activities, practices and outputs, and reward “early sharing and open collaboration”;
- “open science skills” are to be valued and “team science and collaboration” to be recognized as expressing the diversity in research roles and careers.

The agreement also establishes 10 commitments that the signatory organizations will undertake.

Box 16. Core and supporting commitments

Core commitments

- Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
- Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
- Abandon the inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular the inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
- Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Supporting commitments

- Three commitments to pilot and enable the move towards new criteria, tools and processes for research assessment
- Three commitments to facilitate mutual learning, communicate progress and ensure that new approaches are evidence-informed

CoARA advocates for a comprehensive transformation in research assessment, requiring diverse avenues to both validate and disseminate its conclusions.

4.2 CoARA

CoARA stands for a global Coalition comprised of research funding organisations, research performing organisations, national/regional assessment authorities and agencies, as well as associations of these organisations, learned societies, and other relevant organisations. All of these entities are signatories of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. Together, they will collaborate to enable systemic reform based on shared principles within a stipulated timeframe. Furthermore, they aim to facilitate information exchanges and mutual learning among all parties keen on enhancing research assessment practices. As of 31 July 2023, the Coalition has grown to include 527 organisations, with five EELISA HEIs also being members of CoARA (BME, SNS, SSSA, UNSTPB, UPM).

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CoARA's vision asserts that the assessment of research, researchers, and research organisations should acknowledge the variety of outputs, practices, and activities that bolster the quality and impact of research. Such assessments should emphasize qualitative judgment, peer reviews, and the judicious use of quantitative indicators.

Actively championing a systemic alteration in research assessment, CoARA employs a diverse array of channels to test and convey its findings.

Formation of the First CoARA Working Groups and National Chapters

The Coalition's aspiration to reshape the prevailing research assessment landscape takes a decisive stride with the inauguration of its first Working Groups and National Chapters, chosen from a pool of submitted proposals.

Central to CoARA's objective is the establishment of Working Groups. These groups, formed through a bottom-up approach and voluntary participation by members, function as "communities of practice." They foster mutual learning and cooperation on distinct subjects. Engaged members will share insights, gain from one another's experiences, and collaborate on generating outputs to enhance research assessment and fortify their commitments. Presently, CoARA collaborates with ten Working Groups and the initial five National Chapters, all of which have received approval to commence their activities.

Box 17. CoARA's working groups

The 10 working groups currently are:

- Supporting the alignment of research assessment systems with CoARA in biomedical disciplines through administrative reforms and governance
- Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment
- Improving practices in the assessment of research proposals
- Early-and-mid-Career Researchers (EMCRs) – Assessment and Research Culture
- Reforming Academic Career Assessment (ACA)
- Experiments in Assessment – Idea generation, co-creation, and piloting
- Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review
- Multilingualism and language biases in research assessment
- Responsible metrics and indicators
- Towards Transformations: Transdisciplinarity, Applied/Practice-Based Research, and Impacts

The five National Chapters currently are Italy, Norway, Poland, Spain, and Ukraine.

First Call for Working Groups and National Chapters. On 28 March 2023, CoARA initiated a call to all Coalition members for proposals of Working Groups and National Chapters. This marked the first such call since the Coalition's inception in December 2022.

Compositions of Working Groups. CoARA aims to establish three types of Working Groups: interest, discipline, and institutional communities. The goal is to build upon existing community initiatives and bring additional value. A key priority in forming these Working Groups is inclusivity, ensuring participation from organizations of various scales and types, spanning different geographical regions, and including participants from all career stages. The selection process began with Expressions of Interest submitted by 27 April. This was followed by

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community discussions, culminating in full working group proposals by 6 June. Applicants were informed about the selection results on 13 July 2023, accompanied by a brief evaluation report.

National Chapters. Furthermore, CoARA is soliciting National Chapter proposals. These Chapters will advance CoARA's objectives by facilitating knowledge exchange, mutual learning, and addressing CoARA-specific concerns within individual countries. While there's no cap on the total number of National Chapters, currently, only one chapter per country is permitted. National Chapter proposals will be evaluated monthly, starting from 6 June 2023.

The inaugural CoARA Call for Working Group proposals witnessed an impressive response. By the first cut-off date for Expressions of Interest, 32 Working Groups and 6 National Chapters were registered. The progression entailed the development of comprehensive proposals, which were due by 6 June.

These Expressions of Interest presented innovative ideas or actionable steps aligned with the principles and commitments of the RRA Agreement. Here are some notable insights related to Open Science and OS incentives drawn from these proposals:

- Contemporary assessment methodologies that consider open science practices are evolving, emphasizing the importance of staying updated with innovations and collating a repository of research assessment alternatives for active engagement within the CoARA community.
- Potential research evaluation methodologies encompass open science, open peer review, narrative-based assessment, and evaluations involving stakeholders or the broader community, aiming to enhance research quality and impact.
- Recognitions and rewards can be instrumental in driving systemic shifts. Current challenges such as the narrowly defined success metrics and hyper-competition, which can deter productive behaviors, need reevaluation.
- Questions arise on reconciling centralized research assessments, which inherently foster competition, with the principles of Open Science.
- The traditional “publish or perish” model and its drawbacks need reconsideration in research assessment.
- Concerns revolve around ensuring impartiality in peer reviews, especially when centralized entities oversee the process.

Keeping the Discussion Going: Knowledge Sharing Platform. CoARA unveiled a platform to foster discussions, inviting member organization representatives keen on participating in these debates to seek platform access.

The 2023 Call for Working Groups and National Chapters Continues. Come autumn 2023, a second (and final for the year) cut-off for Working Group proposals will be introduced. These will undergo Steering Board reviews by year-end (specific dates forthcoming). Meanwhile, National Chapter proposals are welcomed anytime, with monthly reviews by the Steering Board.

4.3 Developing the EELISA COsMPAS – a digital mechanism for supporting OS

The EELISA INNOCORE framework, designed for promoting and adopting OS, is grounded on four primary pillars: the **OS Toolkit**, the **Methodological Guide**, the **OSAPs**, and the **OS Ambassadors Network**. While this framework seamlessly integrates with current policies and practices, it further enriches them by offering descriptors, indicators, and actions to help navigate various levels of OS proficiency.

Central to this framework is the introduction of a digital tool aimed at weaving together metrics and best practices for more strategic OS planning and implementation. Beyond its

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functional capabilities, the tool adds to an academic career structure that fosters outputs, practices and behaviours to maximise contributions to a shared research knowledge system.

For the successful rollout of the EELISA INNOCORE Common Mechanism—a strategy and tool designed to enable, measure, and reward OS practices—it is vital to gain the commitment of both staff and leadership. To encapsulate these best practices in a dynamic manner, we introduce the **EELISA COsMPAS (Common Open Science Mechanism for Practices, Assessment, and Support)**. This digital tool comprises various modules tailored to enhance OS proficiency.

The COsMPAS tool aims to provide support for universities in developing, managing, and assessing Open Science activities. It boasts a multi-layer architecture (see Figure 6), with each layer addressing a specific functionality of the platform.

At the top, we find the **User Interface Layer**, which provides a dashboard showcasing ongoing activities, metrics, and access points. Below this, the main modules of the platform address the assessment of Open Science as follows:

- **Open Science Practices:** These cover Open Access Publishing, Research Data Management, Skills and Training, as well as Open Science and Rewards.
- **Open Science Planning:** This includes the OSAP generator and a shared workspace.
- **Open Science Metrics and Indicators:** This encompasses assessment practices and metrics dashboards.

At the base of the architecture, there are layers that bolster the platform's functionality:

- Security and Compliance Layer,
- Analytics and Feedback Loop, and
- Backend Layer.

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Figure 6. The COsMPAS Tool – proposed architecture

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In summary, COsMPAS is envisioned to be a comprehensive platform that not only supports open science practices but also fosters a culture of collaboration, transparency, and continuous learning.

Conclusions

The D3.5 report was designed to set the groundwork for the creation of the COsMPAS digital mechanism, targeting OS recognition, incentives, and rewards within the EELISA INNOCORE Consortium. The report provided an extensive overview of key policy developments. It also encompassed a comprehensive review of both international practices and those specific to EELISA. Moreover, several strategies for OS I&R were pinpointed and analyzed.

At the heart of the COsMPAS mechanism is the collaborative exchange of practices and insights. Its purpose is to bolster university partners in their endeavors related to OS implementation. A pivotal feature of this mechanism is the adoption of next-generation indicators and metrics. However, it is crucial to highlight that the European perspective on this matter is evolving, and a unified consensus remains elusive. In 2021, the Commission initiated a significant shift in the world of research assessment. After extensive consultations with global stakeholders, they released a pivotal report hinting at the need for reform. By the end of 2022, this effort culminated in the establishment of the Coalition CoARA. CoARA's guiding principles emphasize Open Science practices, moving away from conventional research metrics towards a more inclusive and qualitative approach. Their focus is not just on openness but also on gender equality, diversity, and equal opportunities within research.

Within the current framework, the COsMPAS mechanism emerges as a pivotal tool, designed to enhance collaboration and solidify commitment to Open Science. However, uncertainties about its evolution and broader application persist. There are inquiries regarding whether COsMPAS is exhaustive in its scope and if it successfully encompasses all pertinent aspects. The consortium's strategy for devising metrics is yet another area that seeks clarity. Furthermore, the practical implementation of COsMPAS prompts questions, especially concerning the alignment between institutional aims and consortium objectives, the selection process, and subsequent refinement of indicators and metrics, and the conversion of COsMPAS into a digital tool tailored for RPOs. These pressing issues are slated to be tackled in upcoming endeavors within EELISA INNOCORE.

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Annexes

Annex 1: A state-of-the-art on initiatives and literature to reform research(er) assessment and incentivise and reward Open Science

A view to **rewarding and incentivising** Open Science. Some specific input emerging from the landscaping exercise that can be of background or direct relevance **to this topic** for interventions/actions and for indicators and metrics.

The landscaping has highlighted a series of **policy papers** produced by the networks/organisations reviewed above that stress the need for reformed research assessment.

1. Policy papers

- The 2012 San Francisco [Declaration on Research Assessment](#) (DORA)
- The 2015 [Leiden Manifesto](#) for research metrics
- SPARC Europe 2015 Briefing paper [Better ways to evaluate research and researchers](#)
- The 2017 European Commission report on [rewards, incentives and recognition for researchers practicing open science](#)²²
- European University Association's 2019 paper [Research Assessment in the Transition to Open Science](#)
- MCAA's 2019 report [Towards Responsible Research Career Assessment](#)
- Science Europe 2020 [Position statement on research assessment processes](#)
- UNESCO's 2020 [Recommendation on Open Science](#)
- The 2021 European Commission report [Towards a reform of the research assessment system](#)"
- YERUN 2021 [Reforming research assessment in Europe: YERUN's take on the issue](#),
- CoARA and the 2022 [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#)
- CoNOSC 2022 [report on reforming research assessment](#)
- Science Europe 2022 [Agreement on reforming research assessment processes](#)
- YERUN 2022 [position on the agreement of research assessment and the CoARA initiative and Rethinking Academic Careers: cultural change as key bottleneck to be addressed](#).

2. Practical tools

Possible interventions /particularly relevant examples are summarised as follows:

- The ORFG [Incentivization Blueprint](#) provides funders with a stepwise approach to adjusting their incentivisation schemes. The three steps cover: Policy development and declarations; Implementation; Engagement.
- The report "[Reimagining Academic Career Assessment: Stories of innovation and change](#)", together with the [accompanying online repository](#) bring together and analyse case studies in responsible academic career assessment. This is a joint initiative of EUA, DORA and SPARC Europe, to serve as a source of inspiration for universities and other actors looking to improve their academic career assessment practices.
- Science Europe, in the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#), proposes "Annex 3 – Reform journey: a suggested process for achieving the Commitments" and "Annex 4 – Toolbox: practical tools and options to consider".
- DORA has produced a toolkit of resources, including a practical guide for research evaluators, the *Building Blocks for Impact* (one pager that outlines the variety of academic achievements and outcomes that could be considered "impactful"), *De-biasing Committee Composition and Deliberative Processes* (one page brief on the evaluation process for hiring, promotion and tenure), [SPACE to evolve academic](#)

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assessment: A rubric for analysing institutional conditions and progress indicators and the Workshop kit to introduce the SPACE rubric.

- OPENAire provides the ASSESS portfolio service that tracks, monitors and evaluates research. This service provides measures and indicators on Open Science trends and impact, and can help organisations shape their policies and actions.

3. The landscaping has also resulted in knowledge in terms of frameworks / Indicators and metrics

The LERU policy paper (2022) A Pathway towards Multidimensional Academic Careers represents a Framework for the Assessment of Researchers. The framework proposes three perspectives of assessment:

- multidimensional perspective, focusing on the diversity of contributions that is expected from academics today (research dimension / education dimension / public engagement and outreach / service to the institution / other dimensions);
- developmental perspective, focusing on personal growth and development of true leadership (leadership in academia / collaboration and innovation)
- contextual perspective, taking into account the particular context of the researcher who is under assessment (professional context / personal context).

CESAER White Paper on New Generation Metrics suggests a set of 'next generation metrics' primarily driven towards interesting and suitable metrics for universities of Science and Technology. The metrics are categorised into Input, Process, Output and Impact. They are designed to be SMART and are divided into:

- Science metrics: set of indicators for measuring research performance through open science.
 - Education metrics: a set of indicators that provide essential information on the readiness of higher education to provide their graduates with the skills needed in the 21st century
 - Innovation metrics: set of indicators relating to the universities involvement in open innovation
- The White Paper also considers a move towards "progressive metrics".

PLOS presents Altmetrics as a way to assess the impact of research publications. Indicators come from the following sources: Viewed; Cited; Recommended; Discussed; Saved.

In close connection (building on work by PLOCS, SPARC has prepared a primer on Article-Level Metrics. This document provides input to a framework of article level metrics, considering five distinct categories: Usage; Captures; Mentions; Social Media; Citations.

Plan S Principle on Responsible Research Assessment and Evaluation states that "when assessing research outputs during funding decisions, cOAlition S funders will make decisions based on the intrinsic merit of the work and not the publication channel, its impact factor (or other journal-level metrics), or the publisher". They take into account the key dimensions summarised in The Metric Tide as: Robustness; Humility; Transparency; Diversity; Reflexivity. cOAlition S has also set up a framework for Monitoring the effects of Plan S on Research and Scholarly Communication.

EUA's 2020 report Exploring Higher Education Indicators explores what kind of education indicators are used by external quality assurance agencies, funding mechanisms and international university rankings and whether they are fit for purpose. It examined three external tools that use indicators and have an impact on higher education institutions: external quality assurance, funding formulae, and rankings. This report covers indicators related to education in the broad sense, encompassing learning and teaching, but also the overall learning experience and environment.

The SCOPE Framework for Research Evaluation is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as check existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation.

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4. Networks and working groups identified above, including but not limited to the following

- The EOSC Association research careers, recognition and credit task force (in addition to the EOSC Executive Board)
- UNESCO Working Group on the Open Science monitoring framework
- The Guild Research Careers & Assessment working group
- CERN Open Science Working Group (currently developing the roadmap on CoARA - expected before end 2023)
- EUA working group on Science 2.0 and Open Science
- cOAlition S Research Assessment Task Group
- Science Europe Open Science working group
- OpenAIRE and National Open Access Desks
- Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), which is expected to function through working groups
- CoNOSC, given its importance at the level of OS national policies and for its recent focus on Research Assessment voted as a priority topic by its members in in 2022, as well as 2023.

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Annex 2: Relevant documents and developments supporting OS

- [2012 Recommendation](#) of the European Commission on access to and preservation of scientific information and its [2018 update](#),
- [the Horizon 2020 Guidelines on the rules of open access to scientific publications and research data](#),
- the [Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council establishing Horizon Europe - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination](#) (COM/2018/435 final)
- the [Proposal for a Decision of the European Parliament and of the Council on establishing the specific programme implementing Horizon Europe - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation](#) (COM/2018/436 final)

Important developments at EU-level related to Open Science/ Open Access such as:

- The [2016 European Council Conclusions](#) on the transition towards an Open Science system;
- [the “Plan S” and “cOAlition S”](#);
- the developments of the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\) and in particular the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#), the action lines of the [European Open Science Policy Platform](#),
- the Communication [“A new ERA for Research and Innovation”](#) and the 2019 EU Directive [on open data and the re-use of public sector information](#),
- the Report [“Towards a 2030 Vision on the Future of Universities in Europe”](#). In addition, the document also takes into consideration other related reports from university associations like EUA’s [“Perspectives on the new European Research Area from the university sector”](#) and [“Universities without walls: A vision for 2030”](#), the Guild of European research intensive universities [“Looking to the Future: the Guild’s Vision for Europe’s Universities”](#) and other associations like the Science Europe practical guide to the [“International Alignment of Research Data Management”](#).

The proposed document draws heavily on the UNESCO Open Science policy development process and [UNESCO Open Access policy development guidelines](#), the [MedOANet guidelines for Open Access](#), [PASTEUR4OA Toolkit](#) and [Policy Guidelines](#), the [RECODE project](#) policy recommendations for Open Access policies to research data, the [LEARN project](#) Model Research Data Management Policy, and the [SPARC Europe report on Open Data and Open Science policies in Europe](#).

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Annex 3: Glossary

<p>Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment</p>	<p>A collaborative framework established to guide modifications in evaluating research, researchers, and research-performing organizations. Its primary aim is to optimize the quality and societal impact of research endeavors. The ARRA delineates foundational principles, pledges, and a timeline for enacting these reforms. Additionally, it stipulates guidelines for a Coalition (see CoARA) of entities united in their intent to realize the outlined changes in assessment practices.</p> <p>Final version of the Agreement</p>
<p>Charter for Researchers</p>	<p>A set of general principles and requirements specifying the roles, responsibilities, and entitlements of researchers as well as of employers and/or funders of researchers.</p> <p>Charter for Researchers</p>
<p>CoARA</p>	<p>A collaborative consortium composed of research funding entities, research-performing organizations, regional and national assessment authorities, relevant associations, learned societies, and other pertinent bodies. CoARA's members have endorsed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment, signifying their collective pledge to institute alterations in research assessment methodologies. As a unified front, they commit to mutually supporting and drawing lessons from each other throughout the transformation process.</p> <p>CoARA</p>
<p>Incentives</p>	<p>Measures or stimuli introduced with the intention to motivate and encourage specific behaviors or actions in researchers. In the context of Open Science, incentives might include financial support, access to exclusive resources, or preferential consideration in certain academic processes, all aimed at promoting open research practices.</p>
<p>Narrative CV</p>	<p>A narrative CV is a résumé style in an application that directs to written descriptions of contributions and accomplishments that showcase a variety of skills and expertise. Narrative CVs are produced typically by responding to a series of open-ended questions.</p> <p>More information</p>
<p>Responsible Research Assessment</p>	<p>It can be defined as “an umbrella term for approaches to assessment which incentivise, reflect and reward the plural characteristics of high-quality research, in support of diverse and inclusive research cultures”.</p>
<p>Recognition</p>	<p>The act of formally acknowledging and giving special attention to certain behaviors, achievements, or efforts of researchers, without necessarily providing a tangible benefit. In the Open Science context, recognition may involve public commendation, certificates, or mention in institutional communications for those who excel in making their work openly accessible and collaborative.</p>
<p>Rewards</p>	<p>Tangible or intangible benefits given to researchers post their action, as a form of appreciation for their contributions or achievements. Within the realm of Open Science, rewards can range from monetary bonuses, publication opportunities, conference invitations, or enhanced research</p>

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	visibility, acknowledging the efforts put into adhering to open research practices.
Structured CV	A structured CV is a type of curriculum vitae (CV) that follows a standard format and structure.

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